

BIODIVERSITY

Data Sharing in Biodiversity

Many organisms move across borders or have a global distribution. In the discipline of Biodiversity it is therefore important to collect, aggregate and exchange data globally. Global initiatives and communities, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility ([GBIF](#)) and the Biodiversity Information Standards ([TDWG](#)), not only play an important role in building technical bridges but also help to build social bridges. Significant progress has been made on issues like liberating biodiversity data from literature, semantic enhanced publishing, industrial scale digitisation of objects, common data exchange formats and community curation of data.

Biodiversity has specific approaches to the planning, acquisition, processing and storage of data collected and generated, but the discipline is also closely related to other domains of research such as Agriculture, Biomedical Life Sciences, Environmental Sciences, Earth Sciences and Biochemistry, and researchers may benefit from the resources, methodologies, and services developed for these fields.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Methods and Documentation

- [FAIRsharing](#)
- [LIFEWATCH ERIC](#)
- [RDMkit](#)
- [FAIRDOME-SEEK](#)
- [Open Bio Maps](#)
- [ELIXIR Core Data Resources](#)
- [EcoPortal](#)
- [AgroPortal](#)

Methods and Documentation

- [Biodiversity Information Standards \(TDWG\)](#)
- [DarwinCore Archive](#)
- [Access to Biological Data \(ABCD\)](#)
- [Ecological Metadata Language \(EML\)](#)
- [Open Traits Network](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Biodiversity researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

Finding and Depositing Data

- [Global Biodiversity Information Facility \(GBIF\)](#)
- [Biodiversity Literature Repository \(BLR\)](#)
- [Biodiversity Heritage Library \(BHL\)](#)
- [Biodiversity Knowledge Hub \(BKH\)](#)
- [TreatmentBank](#)
- [European Nucleotide Archive \(ENA\)](#)
- [Barcode of Life Data \(BOLD\)](#)
- [DataONE](#)
- [Global Biotic Interactions \(GloBI\)](#)
- [Ocean Biodiversity Information System \(OBIS\)](#)
- [World Register of Marine Species \(WoRMS\)](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [BiodiFAIRse](#)
- [TDWG Community](#)
- [SPNHC](#)
- [CETAF](#)
- [ENVRI](#)
- [GEO BON](#)
- [DiSSCo](#)
- [ILTER](#)
- [iNaturalist](#)
- [ECSA](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [Biodiversity Data Integration IG](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [ELIXIR Bridging Force IG](#)
- [RDA/TDWG WG on Metadata Standards](#)
- [Improving Global Agricultural Data \(IGAD\) Community of Practice](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for biodiversity data in Open Science?

“Many researchers in the field work with data that isn’t very big, which makes it possible for them to work on their own. There isn’t a big emphasis on training in standards that enable sharing and the integration of their data into domain-specific repositories. Data that is shared tends to be limited by very specific agreements among projects.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with biodiversity data?

“EOSC connects a lot of global infrastructures which are key to the reuse of biodiversity data. Universities are starting to provide more degree training in open science, but there is still a need for knowledge hubs, meetings and events where the community works towards being more FAIR and compatible. The team I work with at Meise Botanic Garden has benefitted a lot from being part of an inclusive global community.”

— [Sofie Meeus](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Biodiversity

CHEMISTRY

Data Sharing in Chemistry

Chemistry studies the composition, structure, and properties of substances and the transformations that they undergo. Thus, all data generated throughout such a study can be considered chemistry data, and these data can be found in general-purpose repositories/databases, like Zenodo, or in repositories tailored to specific subdomains such as analytical or computational chemistry. Much of the data produced is reported in widely used tabular file formats (e.g. CSV) but molecular structures can be represented by custom formats like InChi or SMILES. Related fields such as biology and materials science may also be good sources for additional resources and tools, and are included in the lists below.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Data and Processing

- [NFDI4Chem knowledge database](#)
- [Chemotion](#)
- [ChemSpider](#)
- [PDB](#)
- [AiiDA](#)
- [ILL Data Portal](#)

Methods and Documentation

- [FAIRsharing Chemistry standards](#)
- [Unified Data Model standard format](#)
- [InChi](#)
- [SMILES](#)

Depositing Data

- [Catalysis Hub](#)
- [Chemotion](#)
- [iochem-bd](#)
- [NOMAD](#)
- [RADAR4Chem](#)
- [HAL](#)
- [ICSD](#)
- [MassBank](#)
- [PubChem](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Chemistry researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

Community and Professional Supports

- [NFDI4Cat](#)
- [NFDI4Chem](#)
- [IUPAC](#)
- [DECHEMA](#)
- [IUCr](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [RDA Chemistry Research Data Interest Group](#)
- [Research Data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science Community Interest Group](#)
- [FAIRsharing WG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

RDA for Disciplines

What are the challenges for chemistry data in Open Science?

“Work in the lab is still manual, and non-digital data is a huge struggle to make open. [Electronic Lab Notebooks](#) will make a big difference to help labs talk the same digital language. As for social supports, the [Research Data Alliance](#) is the best place for conversations around open science – with people who are already into Open Science.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with chemistry data?

“EOSC provides the workflows and tools that can help to change the manual acquisition process, making it easier to share. I think it will be important to onboard tools and workflows from smaller research projects as well as leading international groups.”

— [Pedro Mendes](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Catalysis

CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE ARCTIC

Data Sharing in Arctic Climate research

The arctic is an interesting, special and fragile region that poses its own unique needs, opportunities and challenges when it comes to data: Geopolitically many nations pursue their own interests, research and exploration in the arctic and its resources. Climatologically the arctic is a key place to study climate change: Due to increased melting of the snow and ice covers in the arctic, temperature increase and its effects accelerates faster here than the global warming average. Interdisciplinary research and pan-arctic collaboration is key to both efficient data collection and field campaigns, as well as for monitoring and understanding the effects of climate change. There are a number of international organisations and committees encouraging collaboration in this research area, as well as emerging discipline-specific repositories to support the access, reuse, and deposit of arctic and ocean data.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Data and Processing

- [Barcelona Dust Regional Center \(BRDC\)](#)
- [Climadjust](#)
- [Cos4Bio](#)
- [Earthcube GeoCODES](#)
- [EcoPortal](#)
- [INTERACT Data Portal](#)
- [ICOS Data Portal](#)
- [Polar Data Discovery Enhancement Research \(POLDER\)](#)
- [SIOS](#)
- [openLCA platform](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Arctic Climate Change researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

Methods and Documentation

- [CIMPAL](#)
- [ENES Data Space](#)
- [Lifecycle Initiative](#)
- [Ocean Best Practices \(OBPS\)](#)
- [QGreenland](#)

Depositing Data

- [Arctic Data Center](#)
- [Biological & Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office \(BCO-DMO\)](#)
- [CESNET DataCare](#)
- [ICES/CIEM](#)
- [PANGAEA](#)
- [Sea Scientific Open Data Publication \(SEANOE\)](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [Arctic Council](#)
- [Arctic Data Committee](#)
- [EMODnet for Arctic Stakeholders](#)
- [International Arctic Science Committee](#)
- [International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic \(INTERACT\)](#)
- [International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry \(IUPAC\)](#)
- [United Nations Disaster Risk Reduction \(UNDRR\) PreventionWeb](#)
- [Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management \(SCADM\)](#)
- [Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks \(SAON\)](#)
- [iNaturalist](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [ESES IG](#)
- [Weather, climate and air quality IG](#)
- [Marine Data Harmonization IG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for climate change data in Open Science?

“Climate change researchers are working in a diverse landscape of stakeholders and funding comes from a variety of national programmes, EU initiatives, and private foundations. Researchers working in this area have concerns about how fieldwork data may be interpreted; a feeling of responsibility. Field campaigns and results are subject to limited infrastructure support and quick changes in weather, and the data is big—ensuring long-term continuity of data storage can be difficult with project-funded work.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with climate change data?

“EU funded initiatives are making it possible for research stations to make their data available, reducing the need for projects to re-collect or carry out additional fieldwork in sensitive locations. The EOSC Portal is becoming an important space for sharing this research across borders, and for accessing tools to manipulate and analyse big data. EOSC is already having an impact on the ability for researchers working with climate change data to develop a common approach.”

— [Jonas Koefoed Roemer](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Arctic Data Community, Ecosystems and Climate Change

CULTURAL HERITAGE

Data Sharing in Cultural Heritage

A significant amount of the world's cultural heritage data is made available through the websites of publicly-funded memory institutions, often referred to as 'GLAM' organisations (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums), although this only scratches the surface of what is potentially available in non-digitized holdings. Cultural heritage data may also be derived from private collections, publications, letters, websites, social media, performances and events, interviews, archaeological sites, architecture, and other games and experiential outputs. Much of the work of cultural heritage researchers is still in finding, accessing, digitizing, and further contextualizing these sources of information, while navigating legal and moral cultural rights.

Metadata records which describe the features, location, origins, and ownership of physical artworks, archival records, artifacts, or other non-digital sources of information, are important to this work. The use of controlled vocabularies, descriptive metadata standards, rights statements, open file formats, and persistent identifiers ensure cultural heritage data is made understandable and equitably accessible for reuse.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Finding and Depositing Data

- [Ariadne Portal](#)
- [DANS](#)
- [DARIAH-DE Repository](#)
- [Digital Repository of Ireland](#)
- [E-RIHS: Europeana](#)
- [Getty Open Content Program](#)
- [Heritage Research Hub](#)
- [HathiTrust](#)
- [Internet Archive](#)
- [LC Labs](#)
- [Open Context](#)
- [PARADISEC](#)
- [re3data](#)
- [Rijksmuseum](#)
- [SSHOC](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Cultural Heritage researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

Data Curation and Processing

- [ArcGIS](#)
- [ELAN](#)
- [EXMARaLDA](#)
- [Hypothesis](#)
- [NVivo](#)
- [Omeka](#)
- [TEI](#)
- [Transkribus](#)
- [Tropy](#)
- [Voyant Tools](#)

Methods and Documentation

- [CLARIN Learning Hub](#)
- [DARIAH Campus](#)
- [FAIRsharing](#)
- [Identifiers for Heritage Collections](#)
- [Linked Open Vocabularies](#)
- [Programming Historian](#)
- [Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities](#)
- [Software Heritage Archive](#)
- [Sustainable Heritage Network](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [ALLEA](#)
- [Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations](#)
- [European Association for Digital Humanities](#)
- [OPERAS](#)
- [SSHOC Heritage Studies](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [Libraries for Research Data IG](#)
- [Archives and Records Professionals for Research Data IG](#)
- [International Indigenous Data Sovereignty IG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for cultural heritage data in Open Science?

“Data is not really a term that a lot of researchers in cultural heritage would use to describe their work. There’s some hesitation when it comes to the methodological implications of collecting and re-presenting primary sources, often drawn from public collections, as datasets, but significant barriers also arise from unclear usage licences or limited descriptive and technical metadata associated with those original resources, which are critical to their interpretation and reuse.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with cultural heritage data?

“Data availability is so important to cultural heritage work, and there are still a lot of potential data resources that are siloed and difficult to access digitally. Through platform support and training opportunities, EOSC can help ensure data is surfaced from all kinds of organisations, not just the well-funded major research libraries, archives, and museums. EOSC is a place where a diversity of resources can be connected and made visible.”

— [Beth Knazook](#)

Research Data Project Manager, Digital Repository of Ireland RDA and the Digital Humanities

EARTH, SPACE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

Data Sharing in the Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences

The Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences rely heavily on data to support research and decision-making in areas such as environmental policy and management. Open and FAIR data are particularly important in this field because they enable researchers to collaborate and build upon each other's work, leading to more impactful and informed research. Data may pertain to the land, atmosphere, and other natural phenomena, but can also include data about people, making the [CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance](#) an equally valuable resource in guiding data collection and reuse in this growing community of research. The resources provided here have been suggested by members of the RDA community and are not exhaustive. Resources appropriate researchers in ESES, from data curation to data preservation, may also be found in adjacent fields such as [eg. Chemistry, Biodiversity...]

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Data and Processing

- [Blue-cloud](#)
- [British Oceanographic Data Centre \(BODC\)](#)

- [CEDA Archive](#)
- [Climate-ADAPT](#)
- [Copernicus](#)
- [Geological Survey Ireland \(GSI\)](#)
- [German Climate Computing Center \(DKRZ\)](#)
- [Global Biodiversity Information Facility \(GBIF\)](#)
- [Global Ocean Observing System](#)
- [Group on Earth Observations \(GEOSS\)](#)
- [IAEA/WHO Network of SSDLs](#)
- [ICOS Carbon Portal](#)
- [IPCC Interactive Atlas](#)
- [IPCC Data Distribution Centre](#)
- [ENVRI](#)
- [European Radiological Data Exchange Platform \(EURDEP\)](#)

[EOSC Portal](#)

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the of researchers and research-supporting organisations in Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

- [FAIR-Ease](#)
- [NASA Transform to Open Science \(TOPS\). Science Data](#)
- [National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration \(NOAA\)](#)
- [Ocean Biodiversity Information System \(OBIS\)](#)
- [Ocean Gliders](#)
- [PANGAEA](#)
- [Predictia](#)
- [PARSEC: SOCIB](#)
- [The Southern Ocean Observing System \(SOOS\)](#)
- [World Climate Research Program \(WCRP\)](#)

Methods and Documentation

- [Climate-ADAPT](#)
- [Earth System Grid Federation \(ESGF\)](#)
- [European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#)
- [European Space Agency \(ESA\)](#)
- [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\)](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [American Geophysical Union \(AGU\)](#)
- [Committee on Earth Observation Satellites \(CEOS\)](#)
- [Earth Science Information Partners \(ESIP\)](#)
- [European Geosciences Union \(EGU\)](#)
- [European Marine Observation and Data Network \(EMODnet\)](#)
- [European Radiation Dosimetry Group \(EURADOS\)](#)
- [European Radioecology Alliance](#)
- [EURAMED](#)
- [EURAMET](#)
- [IOCCG](#)
- [Open Geospatial Consortium \(OGC\)](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [ESIP/RDA Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences IG](#)
- [Geospatial IG](#)
- [Global Water Information IG](#)
- [International Indigenous Data Sovereignty IG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for earth, space and environmental sciences data in Open Science?

“There is good awareness of Open Science within the research community, but the principles and practices have not been traditionally a part of their work; many weren’t trained for it in their doctoral studies and there’s often no time set aside to actually do the work. They’re using tools that support FAIR data, but without the training and preparation, they may not feel confident that they’ve done enough.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with earth, space and environmental sciences data?

“Data quality and availability is very important in this field, and there are a lot of tools that have been developed to generate, upload and use data that can be found through EOSC. Networks still need to be developed to help scientists connect with those working in related geographic areas to share their data. EOSC is already a connection point, and it has the potential to be the communication bridge needed between researchers.”

— [Lina Sitz](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Ambassador for Earth System Physics/
Data management

LINGUISTICS

Data Sharing in Linguistics

There are many different types of data used in the field of Linguistics, including: documentary data (e.g., text, audio, video), grammaticality judgements, instrumental data (e.g., eye tracking, EEG measurements, spectrograms), experimental data, derived data (e.g., transcriptions, annotations, syntactic treebanks), metadata, lexical data (e.g., dictionaries), language catalogues, computational data, and interview data. Much of this data is shared through domain-specific repositories which support the use of metadata, citation formats, and licences specific to the field (e.g., Tromsø Recommendations, CLARIN licences), but the data may also be shared in national or general repositories. Some linguistic data is shared via other types of websites (e.g. project websites, personal websites) or in article supplementary files. [The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management](#) (MIT Press, 2022) provides a valuable overview of good practice in collecting, managing, archiving, sharing, and citing data in the field.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Methods and Documentation

- [FAIRsharing](#)
- [The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management](#)
- [The Austin Principles of Data Citation in Linguistics](#)

- [CLARIN Licences](#)
- [Tromsø Recommendations for Citation of Research Data in Linguistics](#)

Learning about Languages

- [Ethnologue](#)
- [Glottolog](#)
- [Arctic Indigenous Peoples languages and revitalization](#)

Data Management and Processing

- [SSH Open Marketplace](#)
- [SIL](#)
- [ELAN](#)
- [Praat](#)

Finding and Depositing Data

- [Virtual Language Observatory](#)
- [CLARIN](#)
- [LDC Catalog](#)
- [CESSDA DC Data Catalogue](#)
- [The Language Archive](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Linguistics researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

- [Language Archive Cologne](#)
- [Tromsø Repository of Language and Linguistics](#)
- [Child Language Data Exchange System \(CHILDES\)](#)
- [Endangered Languages Archive \(ELAR\)](#)
- [Tekstlaboratoriet](#)
- [Ortolang](#)
- [Computation Resource for South Asian Languages \(CoRSAL\)](#)
- [Pangloss Collection](#)
- [Kaipuleohone Language Archive](#)
- [Native American Languages Collections \(NALC\)](#)
- [Paradisec](#)
- [Archive of the Indigenous Languages of Latin America \(AILLA\)](#)
- [Center for Native American and Indigenous Research \(CNAIR\), American Philosophical Society](#)
- [California Language Archive \(CLA\)](#)
- [Repository and Workspace for Austroasiatic Intangible Heritage \(RWAAI\)](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [CLARIN](#)
- [Collaboratory for Indigenous Data Governance](#)
- [DARIAH](#)
- [Digital Endangered Languages and Musics Archives Network \(DELAMAN\)](#)
- [Global Indigenous Data Alliance \(GIDA\)](#)
- [Linguistics Data Consortium \(LDC\)](#)
- [Linguistic Society of America](#)
- [Huma-Num](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [Linguistics Data IG](#)
- [International Indigenous Data Sovereignty IG](#)
- [Psychological Data IG](#)
- [Sensitive Data IG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for linguistic data in Open Science?

“Linguistics has a history of developing data practices in relative isolation by subfield, lab, and researcher, but as a discipline, we could strongly benefit from broader discussions about the role of data and best practices in research data management. Also, older, unpublished linguistic data often contains personal information, and it can be difficult to make this data openly available so long after the point of collection. Historical linguistics data is also often sensitive in nature, especially when it concerns the words and languages of historically marginalized peoples.

The [RDA Linguistics Interest Group](#) was formed to provide guidance about how to make linguistic research transparent and reproducible all while taking into account any relevant ethical and legal issues. Outputs of the Interest Group should be relevant to all subfields of the discipline and all types of linguistic data, while simultaneously acknowledging the diversity of sources, and should as such facilitate the researchers’ decisions on whether and how to archive, cite and share their data.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with linguistic data?

“There is infrastructure support for the field, particularly in terms of discipline-specific repositories and developments for metadata, as well as initiatives that are providing global support and consensus around aspects of Open Science like data citation and attribution. EOSC will improve repository support for FAIR data, and by creating a European network, it can also provide better connections across infrastructures available globally.”

— [Helene N. Andreassen](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Linguistics

MATERIALS SCIENCES AND ENGINEERING

Data Sharing in Materials Sciences and Engineering

The Materials Sciences and Engineering domain covers a highly heterogeneous community of scientists, including experimentalists and computational scientists, commercial subjects and manufacturing. Open data sharing is still in its early phase, but there are several domain-specific repositories such as NOMAD, DICE, and Materials Commons which enable open data sharing. Material scientists are also very active in the development of electronic laboratory notebooks and laboratory information management systems for automatic data and metadata acquisition. Several ontologies are being developed to improve the interoperability of shared data. Precise characterisation of materials and other samples requires diverse experimental and computational approaches, which increases the importance of sharing workflows and cookbooks, precise instrument description, or, as for engineering, data on a local environment.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Data Management and Processing

- [elabFTW](#)
- [ELN Finder](#)
- [Kadi4Mat](#)
- [NexusLIMS/](#)
- [NOMAD Oasis](#)
- [OpenAIRE Graph](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Materials Sciences and Engineering researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

Methods and Documentation

- [BFO-Ontology](#)
- [Data Management for Beginners](#)
- [Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology \(EMMO\)](#)
- [ICSD](#)
- [Materials Design Ontology](#)
- [Materials Project Seminars](#)
- [Metadata4Eng](#)
- [NFDi4ing Terminology Service](#)
- [OM2: Ontology Units of Measure](#)

Finding and Depositing Data

- [NFDi4ing](#)
- [NOMAD](#)
- [DICE](#)
- [Materials Commons 2.0](#)
- [Materials Project](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [Advanced Materials](#)
- [European Materials Modelling Council](#)
- [Materials Commons Communities of Practice](#)
- [Materials Research Data Alliance \(MaRDA\)](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [FAIR Instrument Data IG](#)
- [Persistent Identification of Instruments WG](#)
- [International Materials Resource Registries WG](#)
- [Sensitive Data IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for materials sciences and engineering data in Open Science?

“Materials Sciences and Engineering is often very site-specific, centred around non-digital objects, local funding streams, and heterogenous research cultures. It can be hard to use instruments and tools if a researcher does not have access through national infrastructure and the tools are not made openly available. Metadata recording is still a manual process, based on paper notebooks and well-established processes that will take time to shift to digital.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with materials sciences and engineering data?

“The research infrastructures that are a part of EOSC are starting to help align practices, as they provide tools and instructions in how to use diverse digital instruments in daily laboratory work. [Electronic Lab Notebooks](#) are beginning to push the field towards automation and machine-actionability. But Open Science is still human-oriented, and reliant on a few people keen to do things properly and show others how they succeeded. [Use cases](#) have been helpful in advancing good research data management practices.”

— [Marek Cebecauer](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Materials Sciences and Engineering

SOCIAL SCIENCES

Data Sharing in the Social Sciences

The Social Sciences is a broad field of research, encompassing “any branch of academic study or science that deals with human behaviour in its social and cultural aspects” ([Britannica](#)). A recent report for the RDA on the current Interest and Working Groups of relevance to this field considered the definition to broadly include the fields of sociology, anthropology, communication sciences, psychology, educational sciences, pedagogics and economics ([RDA Overview for the Social Sciences, 2022](#)).

Social Sciences researchers may work with either or both quantitative and qualitative data. Most researchers will work with sensitive data at some point in their careers which presents ethical and legal issues for data management. Not all sensitive data is alike, with significant variation across the domain in terms of how sensitive data is defined, linked, managed, stored, and reused. Guidance and tools for acquiring and sharing this data in compliance with legal and ethical obligations is the focus of many of the resources listed below.

Where can I find resources and tools for...

Finding and Depositing Data

- [CESSDA Data Catalogue](#)
- [CIS Data Bank](#)
- [DANS](#)
- [Ethnig Survey Data Hub](#)
- [European Commission Joint ResearchCentre Data Catalogue](#)
- [European Data Portal](#)
- [Eurostat](#)
- [FAIRsharing](#)
- [Harvard Dataverse](#)
- [ICPSR](#)
- [Open Science Observatory](#)
- [SSHOC](#)
- [UK Data Archive](#)

EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal is a gateway to many of the innovative services, tools, publications and data listed here, and it is constantly growing with additions from the community of Social Sciences researchers and research-supporting organisations. Do you have a resource that you want to share with others? Consider [onboarding](#) into EOSC.

Methods and Documentation

- [DataCite](#)
- [DDI Profiles](#)
- [European Language Social Science Thesaurus \(ELSST\)](#)
- [FORS Methodological Research Guidance](#)
- [ICPSR Publications on Data Stewardship](#)
- [LinkHub](#)

Community and Professional Supports

- [ARL Advocacy & Public Policy](#)
- [IASSIST](#)
- [SSH Training Community](#)

Learn more about the Research Data Alliance (RDA)

- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Sensitive Data IG](#)
- [Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Legal Interoperability IG](#)
- [RDA/NISO Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)

How to do FAIR and Open Science

- [What is FAIR?](#)
- [FAIR Community Support](#)
- [What is the goal of Open Science?](#)

What are the challenges for social science data in Open Science?

“There are challenges to publishing internationally when research questions and participants may be nation-specific – with global science, you need to make everything comparable. Lack of information and funding to support Open Access opportunities is also a barrier, particularly for the ‘citizen scientists’ contributing to our knowledge of sociology and social work. The people actually doing that work are not always academics in the traditional sense, and we need to educate them and provide opportunities to help them report and analyse what they observe in the field.”

How can EOSC help researchers working with social science data?

“It’s so much easier to collect participant data with access to digital tools. An online survey reaches a much wider audience than someone going door-to-door. EOSC can help researchers to leverage FAIR supporting survey and data collection tools that ensure participant data is managed ethically and responsibly. It’s also an equalising platform, as it exposes information about data and publications across Europe.”

— [Geta Mitrea](#)

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador
for the Social Sciences

